

**IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING DESIGN ACTIVITIES IN
THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS****Satvoldieva Malokhatkhan Azamjonovna**

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Abstract. This article presents the experience of including future technology teachers in innovative project activities. The directions for the effective development of technological education in the region are described. One of the main problems of technological education is highlighted, innovative project activities are proposed to ensure interaction at all levels of technological education with industrial production. The characteristics of innovative project activities are given.

Keywords: future technology teachers, innovative project activities, industrial enterprises, technological education, creative object, students.

INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of solving this problem largely depends on how well the professional training of pedagogical university students – future technology teachers – will be carried out. Today, it is technological education that is positioned as an educational field that provides students with “the opportunity to put into practice knowledge of the fundamentals of science, master the general principles and specific skills of transformative human activity, various forms of information and material culture, as well as the creation of new products and services” [3, p. 2]. Accordingly, it is within this area that preparation for active, creative productive work in the sphere of material production should be implemented.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Separately, it is necessary to highlight the situation that arose in connection with the transition of production to the private sector, which has changed the attitude of the managers of these industries to the training of the younger generation. At best, manufacturing enterprises are limited to one-time material or financial support, and systematic, close cooperation in terms of improving technological education is out of the question.

The situation is also complicated by the fact that “outdated or obsolete means of technological education... do not allow students to fully solve current production, technological and design and research problems in technology lessons and in extracurricular activities” [4, p.

28], which further widens the gap between technological education and the manufacturing sector.

To solve this problem at the Department of Technology and Technical Creativity under the leadership of Professor V.P. Tigrov, work is underway to include future technology teachers in innovative project activities. Innovative project activities differ from project activities in the following ways:

- an innovative project is characterized by objective novelty;
- objective novelty is confirmed by an intellectual property document;
- students are engaged not only in creating creative objects, but also make efforts to implement their developments at industrial enterprises [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inclusion of students in innovative project activities with the aim of establishing a connection between production and technological education covers the following main stages.

The first stage is aimed at involving future technology teachers in innovative project activities. This work is carried out in the first year of study of students, its content includes:

- educational material introducing outstanding works already implemented;
 - study of some techniques for intensifying the search for solutions to creative problems;
 - demonstration of practical examples of solving creative problems. The main goal of this stage is to demonstrate to students how to
- availability of creative work at the inventive level.

The second stage introduces students to practical research work, which is based on the study of technical objects produced at industrial enterprises of the Lipetsk region with their subsequent improvement at the rationalization and inventive levels.

This type of work is carried out in a temporary creative group, which is created by a teacher of the department. Three to four students who have shown interest in a specific object of technology or technology are selected for this group. Then a manufacturing enterprise is selected that produces products in the area of interest, and the teacher of the department negotiates with the managers of the enterprise about creative interaction. One or two consultants are appointed from the enterprise, who also join the group and interact with students remotely via the Internet at a time appointed by the teacher, advising them on technical, technological, and organizational issues. As a rule, from one to one and a half hours per week are spent on such consultations.

The main goal of this stage is to apply previously acquired knowledge in practice, to consolidate skills in implementing innovative project activities.

The interaction of this kind of temporary scientific group would probably not be possible if there was no interest on the part of the manufacturing enterprise in the successful result of creative activity, which ultimately ends in the creation of an object of intellectual property for the enterprise in the form of a patent for an invention or a patent for a utility model.

The third stage involves independent work of students, in which they themselves act as organizers and managers of innovative project activities. Before carrying out innovative project activities, a temporary working group draws up a road map, which in the student's independent work (but already in the role of a group leader) is his internal action plan.

Such a roadmap in its content may vary depending on the object of creative activity, its goals, objectives, logistics, but in its main content it boils down to the following sequence of its implementation [3]:

- 1) identification of the object of innovative design activity and the enterprise producing this object via the Internet;
- 2) formation of a temporary working group to carry out work to improve the facility;
- 3) approval of the work schedule and consultations with production representatives;
- 4) development of a version to improve the object: identification of shortcomings, search for ways to eliminate shortcomings;
- 5) choosing the most effective (economical) option;
- 6) building a model (prototype);
- 7) checking the performance and applicability of the improvement option;
- 8) filling out an application for an object of intellectual property;
- 9) discussion of the results of work by enterprise specialists together with developers;
- 10) identifying ways for further interaction.

The main goal of the third stage is to train future technology teachers in innovative project activities, the presence of which is an integral requirement for the future teacher, who subsequently guides children in the process of introducing them to innovative project activities.

CONCLUSION

The inclusion of future technology teachers in innovative project activities is an effective solution to the task facing the "Technology" subject area, which is to prepare students for productive work in the field of material production and active creative activity. Students, within the framework of innovative project activities, master the most important competencies that allow them to subsequently independently carry out innovative project activities in the status of a teacher (with the transfer of unique experience to students with the possibility of further orientation to the production sector) or an entrepreneur (with experience in creating an

innovative project, established contacts with representatives of other industries and structures that provide assistance to innovative enterprises). Accordingly, the inclusion of future technology teachers in innovative project activities will improve the efficiency of development of the country's innovative economy.

REFERENCES

1. Serebrennikov L.N. Current problems of technological education. Yaroslavl Pedagogical Bulletin. 2010; No. 4: 257 – 261.
2. Raqiboyevna, G. M. (2023). Hereditary Pigmentary Degeneration. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*, 1(10), 146-149.
3. AMINOVA, Z., & KHALILOVA, O. MATERIALS IN ESP COURSES. *Иностранные языки в Узбекистане*. 2019 (3): 83-93.
4. Aminova, Z. P. (2020). THE ESSENTIAL ROLE OF IT IN INCREASING STUDENTS' MOTIVATION. *Modern Science*, (6-4), 90-92.
5. Aminova, Z. P. (2020). WORLD OF EDUCATION ARE USING ELECTRONIC PLATFORM SUCH AS MOODLE SYSTEM. *Modern Science*, (5-1), 276-278.
6. Aminova, Z. P. (2018). Importance of Implementing Pedagogical Technologies to Education System. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (2).
7. Хосиятов, Х. О. (2022). ҚАШҚАДАРЁ ВА СУРХОНДАРЁ ВИЛОЯТЛАРИ МУЗЕЙЛАРИНИНГ НУФУЗЛИ ХАЛҚАРО ТАШКИЛОТЛАР ВА ХОРИЖИЙ МАМЛАКАТЛАР БИЛАН АЛОҚАЛАРИ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 28, 186-190.
8. Хосиятов, Х. О. (2020). МУСТАҚИЛЛИК ЙИЛЛАРИДА ТЕРМИЗ АРХЕОЛОГИЯ МУЗЕЙИ. *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ*, (SI-1№ 4).
9. Khosiyatov, K. O. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ КРАЕВЕДЧЕСКОГО МУЗЕЯ В КАРШИ НА ДУХОВНОСТЬ МОЛОДЁЖИ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 686-692.
10. Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). THE USE OF LITERATURE IN THE LANGUAGE CLASSROOM. *THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD*, 1(2), 196-200.
11. Yusubjonova, M. I., Vallamatova, S. S., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). CONSECUTIVE TRANSLATION AND ITS PECULARITIES. *THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD*, 1(2), 50-55.

12. Agytaevna, A. G. (2023). FUNCTION OF LANGUAGE IN PRESERVATION OF NATIONAL ETHNO-CULTURAL INFORMATION (on the example of materials of the Kazakh language). *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 16, 151-156.
13. Gazizova, L. K., & Ermatova, B. O. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF AGE-RELATED MACULAR DEGENERATION. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 28-34.
14. Gazizova, L. K., & Ermatova, B. O. Prevention of Age-Related Macular Degeneration. *SCHOLASTIC: Journal of Natural and Medical Education*.
15. Ermatova, B. O., & Gazizova, L. K. (2023). RELEVANCE OF OPEN ANGLE GLAUCOMA IN ELDERLY PEOPLE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(21), 26-31.
16. Uralovna, B. Z., & Ravshan o'g'li, A. Y. (2023). Hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatida badiiy ko'chimlarning obyektiv va subyektiv asoslari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 2(2), 9-15.
17. Uralovna, B. Z. (2023). The Place of the Uzbek Language in the World Community. *Genius Repository*, 25, 35-37.
18. Kaipbergenova, S. (2024). APPROACHES IN COMPUTER LINGUADIDACTICS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(1), 255-257.
19. FAYZULLAEVA, S. U. THEMATIC DIRECTIONS OF THE NATURE OF THE LYRICAL EVENING. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (5), 157-159.
20. Isakovna, I. R. (2023). LITERARI THE ROLE OF IMAGE ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUES IN THE PROGRESS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(07), 48-52.
21. Gafurov, B. Z. (2019). RESEARCH OF SEGMENTAL BACKGROUND VALUES OF NAMES OF EXISTING UZBEK LANGUAGE WHICH BEGIN FROM THE AGREEMENT LETTER "K". *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(6), 272-274.
22. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Discourse about the peculiarities of the theme of male gender in advertising texts in Russian and Uzbek (on the material of medical

- vocabulary). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2(2), 4-8.
23. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Discourse about the peculiarities of the theme of male gender in advertising texts in Russian and Uzbek (on the material of medical vocabulary). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2(2), 4-8.
24. Бабаева, Г. (2022). Маданиятлараро мулоқот жараёнидаги муомала маданияти. *Современные лингвистические исследования: зарубежный опыт, перспективные исследования и инновационные методы преподавания языков*, (1), 208-209.
25. Хакимов, М. Ш., Маткулиев, У. И., Ашуров, Ш. Э., & Кодирова, Г. Р. (2022). *Новый взгляд на оценку тяжести кровотечения из варикозно расширенных вен пищевода* (Doctoral dissertation, Узбекистан).
26. Ашурова, О. Ю., & Кодирова, Г. Р. (2020). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭНТЕРАЛЬНОЙ ОКСИГЕНОТЕРАПИИ (КИСЛОРОДНОГО КОКТЕЙЛЯ) В КОМПЛЕКСНОМ ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ГИПОКСИИ И ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ БОЛЕЗНЕЙ ОРГАНОВ ДЫХАНИЯ. *Интернаука*, (46-1), 36-37.
27. Муртазаева, Ф. (2024). ЖЕНСКОЕ НАСИЛИЕ И ЕГО ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ОТПЕЧАТОК В РОМАНЕ ЭМИЛИ БРОНТЕ «ГРОЗОВОЙ ПЕРЕВАЛ». *Interpretation and researches*, 2(1 (23)).
28. Муртазаева, Ф. Р. (2023). ВНУТРЕННИЙ МИР ЖЕНЩИН В АНГЛИЙСКОЙ «ЖЕНСКОЙ ПРОЗЕ». *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(10), 44-48.
29. Муртазаева, Ф. Р. (2023, August). ДИНАМИКА РАСКРЫТИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЗМА В АМЕРИКАНСКОЙ «ЖЕНСКОЙ ПРОЗЕ». In *International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 15-19).
30. The concept of teaching the subject area “Technology” in educational organizations of the that implement basic general education programs (approved by the Ministry of Education of the on December 29, 2018). Available at: <https://docs.edu.gov.ru/document/c4d7feb359d9563f114aea8106c9a2aa>

31. Makhotin D.A. Development of technological education for schoolchildren during the transition to a new technological structure. Education and science. 2017; No. 7: 25 – 40.
32. Tigrov V.P., Dobromyslova O.Yu. Organization of innovative project activities in the center for youth innovative creativity “Novator”. School and production. 2019; No. 1: 51 – 54.